

INTERPRETATION OF ADHESION TENSION DATA.

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When the surface of a solid is in equilibrium with a liquid—vapour interface making a finite contact angle with the solid surface, the well known Young's equation (*Phil. Trans.*, 1805, 96, 65) gives the relation.

$$S_{10} - S_{12} = S_{02} \cos \theta_{02} \quad \dots (i)$$

*where S = Specific free energy of an interface.

0 = Vapour.

1 = Solid.

2 = Organic liquid making an acute contact angle with the solid under investigation.

* The other symbols used in this paper are :—

3 = Water.

4 = Organic liquid having a zero contact angle.

10 = Solid—vapour interface.

12 = Solid—organic liquid interface.

13 = Solid—water interface, etc., etc.

S_{xy} = Specific free energy of xy interface (x or y may be 0, 2, 3 or 4).

θ_{xy} = The angle made by the interface xy with the solid, and measured from the interface towards the solid in the direction xy .

Defining θ_{xy} as above avoids the confusion that arises otherwise (*cf.* Equations connecting A_{12} , A_{13} and θ_{23} , Bartell and Osterhoff, "Colloid Symposium Monograph", 1927, 5, 113; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 548). Moreover it enables one to write down the equations for equilibria at other interfaces merely by symmetry.

Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", 1926, p. 157) calls $S_{10} - S_{12}$, the adhesion tension A_{12} of the liquid against the solid. Bartell and co-workers (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1927, 19, 1277; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1178; 1934, 38, 495; 1935, 39, 11) have described several methods of determining the adhesion tension of liquids. They have further emphasised on the usefulness of these measurements in the determination of (a) the free energy of immersion of a solid in a liquid, (b) the adsorption at solid—liquid interfaces, and (c) the specific surface of adsorbents. The

* The conjugated suffixes 0-4 denote the interface of different phases.

present paper deals with certain theoretical difficulties that arise in the interpretation of adhesion tension data.

The Adhesion Tension of a Non-spreading liquid, i.e., one which makes a finite Contact angle with the Solid.—Harkins and Dahlstrom (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1930, 22, 900) makes a careful distinction between what they call, the final free energy of immersion and the total free energy of immersion. The latter quantity is defined as the free energy change that accompanies the immersion of a unit surface of the dry solid in the liquid. On the other hand, the final free energy of immersion represents the free energy change brought about by immersing a unit area of the solid surface in equilibrium with the saturated vapour of the liquid, into the liquid phase. Harkins has clearly shown that the adhesion tension of a non-spreading liquid is a measure of the final free energy of immersion.

The Adhesion Tension of Water against a Solid which is completely wetted by it, i.e., a Solid against which its Contact angle is zero.—For any liquid making a zero angle of contact with a solid, the adhesion tension as calculated from equation (i) becomes equal to the surface tension of the liquid; this result is as it ought to be since a solid in equilibrium with the vapour of such a liquid gets a continuous adsorption layer of the fluid; the solid surface thus covered with the adsorbed film behaves like the surface of the liquid for all practical purposes in accordance with Langmuir's principle of independent surface action (*Chem. Rev.*, 1921, 6, 647). Thus the immersion of such a solid surface into the liquid involves the same free energy change as the immersion of an equivalent liquid surface. Bartell and co-workers have suggested that equation (i) should not be used to compute the adhesion tension of a spreading liquid. They are of the opinion that the adhesion tension of water against a solid (with which it makes a zero angle of contact) is obtained by measuring θ_{23} , the angle of contact made by the water—non-spreading organic liquid interface with the solid and calculating by means of the equation

$$A_{13} \text{ (of Bartell)} = A_{12} + S_{23} \cos \theta_{23} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

The exact interpretation of A_{13} of Bartell could be had thus: by the application of Young's relation to the solid—organic liquid—water system we get

$$S'_{12} - S'_{13} = S_{23} \cos \theta_{23} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

S'_{12} is the interfacial tension of the interface between the solid and the organic liquid, 2, saturated with water and S'_{13} is that of the inter-

face between the solid and the water saturated with the non-spreading organic liquid. Combining equations (iii) and (i) we get

$$A_{13} \text{ (of Bartell)} = A_{12} + S'_{12} - S'_{13} \quad \dots \text{ (iv)}$$

We could put this equation in the form

$$A_{13} \text{ (of Bartell)} = A_{12} + (S'_{10} - S'_{13}) - (S'_{10} - S'_{12})$$

where S'_{10} is the surface tension of the solid in equilibrium with the vapour of the saturated solution of water in the organic liquid. Thus the A_{13} of Bartell is equal to the final free energy of immersion of the solid in the *anhydrous* non-spreading organic liquid minus the final free energy of immersion of the solid in the nonspreading organic liquid *saturated with water* plus the final free energy of immersion of the solid in water saturated with the organic liquid. Thus the quantity designated by Bartell as the adhesion tension of water is an extremely complicated quantity and does not appear to have the significance attached to it.

The Adhesion Tension of a Spreading Organic Liquid against a Solid; i.e., a Solid against which its Contact angle is zero.—Bartell suggests that A_{14} , the adhesion tension of a spreading organic liquid is to be got by determining the angle of contact made by the water-organic liquid interface with the solid and calculating by means of the equation

$$A_{14} \text{ (of Bartell)} = A_{13} \text{ (of Bartell)} - S_{43} \cos \theta_{43} \quad \dots \text{ (v)}$$

Reasoning as before, the A_{14} of Bartell can be shown to be an extremely complicated quantity (since it can be expressed as the algebraic sum of eight free surface energy terms).

The Explanation of the Observation of Bartell that "The order of decrease of the free surface energies when a polar solid is wetted by each of a series of zero Contact angled Liquids is the same as the order of decrease in free surface energies which occurs when water is brought into contact with the same series of liquids" (Bartell and Hershberger, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1930, 22, 1304; Bartell and Osterhoffs, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 548).

Though the A_{14} values of Bartell have a complicated significance as pointed out in the last section, the values for any set of organic liquids exhibit a striking regularity. If one arranges the organic liquids in the order of increasing A_{14} values, the same is found to be true of that of decreasing S_{43} values also. This interesting correlation can be explained thus. It is to be noted that A_{14} values are obtained by means of equa-

tion (v). Since A_{13} is a constant, the order of increasing A_{14} values is same as the order of decreasing $S_{43} \cos \theta_{43}$ values. The latter quantity is really the difference of the free energy of immersion of the solid (in equilibrium with water and the organic liquid vapours) against the water layer on the one hand and the organic liquid layer on the other. It is well known that liquids similar to water have small interfacial tensions against water, whereas others have high values. The lower the value of S_{43} , the greater will be the similarity in properties of the water and the organic liquid layer and θ_{43} would approach 90° and cause a decrease of values of $\cos \theta_{43}$, since θ_{43} is acute. The order of decrease of values of S_{43} for a series of liquids would thus be more or less the same as that for the values of $\cos \theta_{43}$. Hence the values of $S_{43} \cos \theta_{43}$ would also be of the same order. Therefore the order of increase of A_{14} values and that of increase of A_{34} (or $S_{30} - S_{43}$) values are one and the same. This is what is implied in the statement of Bartell.

Calculation of Adsorption at Solid-liquid Interfaces from Adhesion tension Data.—In order to calculate adsorption at solid—liquid interfaces Bartell and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 466) apply Gibbs equation and derives the relation

$$U = -\frac{1}{RT} \frac{dA_{14}}{d \ln C} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

where U is the Gibbs' adsorption excess, and C is the concentration of the solute in the organic liquid. In deriving this they assume that $A_{14} = S_{10} - S_{14}$ which is obviously not true as shown in third section of the present paper. Thus the values of U do not represent adsorption at the solid—liquid interfaces. It is however found that the U values thus obtained exhibit an interesting correlation to the adsorption at a water—organic liquid interface; we shall proceed to explain why such a correlation obtains. Combining equations (v) and (vi) we get

$$U = -\frac{1}{RT} \frac{d(S_{43} \cos \theta_{43})}{d \ln C} \quad \dots \quad (vii)$$

Considerations similar to those discussed in the last section make it evident that the order of decrease of value of U as given by equation (vii) (for any series of liquids) ought to be the same as the order of decrease of the values of the expression

$$-\frac{1}{RT} \frac{dS_{43}}{d \ln C}.$$

The latter expression is a measure of the adsorption at the water—organic liquid interface. This accounts for the observation of Bartell that "The order of maximum adsorption of a given solute from a series of organic liquids was found to be the same whether silica or water was used as the adsorbent."

That adhesion tension data do not give an idea of the adsorption at the solid—liquid interface becomes evident when one considers the adsorption on silica from ethyl carbonate—benzene mixtures. Bartell's data on adhesion tension (Bartell and Fu, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 1765) indicate that on silica, ethyl carbonate is selectively adsorbed over the entire range of concentrations. Bartell's own experiments with silica gel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 2501) give an S-shaped "apparent adsorption" concentration curve. Apparent adsorption or selectivity, it is to be pointed out, corresponds to the Gibb's adsorption excess (Doss and Rao, *J. Mysore Univ.*, 1935, **8**, 54). Thus there is a disagreement in the adsorption values got from adhesion tension measurements and those got by direct experiments with the silica gel. This difference cannot be attributed to the fact that a plane surface is involved in one case, while capillary action is possible in the other. The effect of proximity of two adsorbing surfaces may now be considered. The closeness as obtained by a capillary of molecular dimensions may mean a greater specificity in adsorption so that in some favourable cases, the finest pores of the adsorbent may be available for only one of the components in the binary mixture. The existence of the finest pores which are accessible to certain substances and not to others may be inferred from Patrick's data on internal gel volumes (Patrick and Opdycke, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 601). Silica gel is found to take up more of water than of benzene or carbon tetrachloride. A few of the measurements made by Patrick have been repeated by the present author. A sample of silica gel on being saturated by the dynamic method with each of the following liquids took 0.331 c.c. of water, 0.327 c.c. of ethyl alcohol, 0.306 c.c. of benzene, and 0.298 c.c. of carbon tetrachloride per g. of gel. This aspect of the problem has been thoroughly investigated by Rao (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 331, 340). Thus a certain amount of space available for water is totally inaccessible for benzene or carbon tetrachloride. Hence, the form of the apparent adsorption-concentration curve would depend upon the nature of the adsorbent. The gel used by Bartell (prepared from nickel silicate) which may be expected to have a large proportion of the wider capillaries showed a lesser capacity for selection (*i.e.*, gave S-shaped curves), whereas the gel used by Jones and Outridge (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1574) and B.S. Rao (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 616) which had a larger

proportion of finer capillaries showed a greater tendency for selective adsorption. Thus one would expect a plane surface of any solid to exert less selective action than a porous adsorbent. So, the disagreement between the adsorption values obtained from adhesion tension data and those by direct measurement with silica gel could be explained if the membrane used in the displacement pressure method consisted of finer pores. But as the radius of the pore in the membrane used by Bartell was of the order of 10^{-4} cm. one would expect a similar tendency for selective adsorption. Therefore, the discrepancy is probably not due to capillary action.

In this connection Bartell and Fu (*loc. cit.*) said "It should be remarked however that this is not a conclusive proof of the inapplicability of the Gibbs' theorem as related to the solid—liquid interface. It is well known that if a substance raises the surface tension of a solvent, the increase is usually very small. If a similar action appears at a solid—liquid interface, the effect of the component with lower adhesion tension may be small when compared with that of one having a higher adhesion tension. The method available at present for the measurement of adhesion tension may not be sufficiently accurate to detect the small increase of adhesion tension due to the addition of a second component (but this is not believed to be the case)". Bartell and Fu treat this anomaly by, what they call a "thermodynamically identical process". It is evident that their procedure is not identical with that of Gibbs' since the conclusions in such a case would have been identical. Thus, their treatment is not rigorous.

There are two other factors to be taken into account while calculating the adsorption from concentrated solutions by making use of Gibbs' equation. First, the concentrations are not identical with activities at higher concentrations. Secondly, Bartell's relation between Gibbs' adsorption excess and the actual concentration of the adsorbed component in the surface layer involves the assumption that the Gibbs' dividing surface lies at the physical interface. But the simple Gibbs' equation gives the $\Gamma_2^{(1)}$ of Guggenheim and Adam (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, A 139, 228) in which case, the above condition is satisfied only in the region of dilute solutions. At higher concentrations, the relationship between the Gibbs' adsorption excess and the actual concentration in the adsorption layer is not given by the formulation of Bartell.

Calculation of the Specific Surface of Adsorbents.—Bartell and Bartell (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2205) have suggested a method of calculating the specific surface of porous adsorbents from data on adhesion tension and the heat of wetting. In the calculations they assume that the adhesion tension is a measure of the total free energy of immersion.

But this is not true as shown in the first three sections of the present paper. Moreover, the experimental results of Bartell and Almy (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 985) show that the absolute values of heat of wetting calculated from adhesion tension data may differ from the actual values by over twenty per cent. Thus the method of calculating the specific surface does not appear to be quite sound.

Value of Adhesion Tension data.—Whereas the correlation of fundamental quantities such as adsorption and total free energy of immersion to adhesion tension data is beset with theoretical difficulties, the extensive work of Bartell seems to be of great value in getting at qualitative or semi-quantitative ideas regarding wetting phenomena. Bartell and Bartell's later paper (*loc. cit.*) shows several new interesting relations between the experimentally determined quantities, the explanation of which may throw further light on the subject.

S U M M A R Y.

It is shown that adhesion tension data of spreading liquids cannot give any definite information regarding (a) the total free energy of immersion of a solid in a liquid (b) adsorption at solid—liquid interface and cannot be used to calculate the specific surface of adsorbents.

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